

Participation in Co-curricular Activities, Communication System and Teachers Job Performance in Secondary Schools in Ekiti State

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Abstract:

The study examined the relationship between participation in co-curricular activities, communication system and teachers job performance in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. The population of the study comprised all 7,177 teachers and 202 principals in all the 202 public secondary schools in the sixteen local government areas in Ekiti State. The sample for this study was 384 respondents comprising 24 principals and 360 teachers drawn from 24 public secondary schools in Ekiti State. Multi-stage procedure which involved simple random was used to select sample for the study. Two instruments tagged "Participation in Co-curricular activities and Communication system Questionnaire" (PCCQ) and "Teachers Job Performance Questionnaire" (TJPQ) were used to collect data. The instruments were validated and found reliable with reliability coefficients of 0.86 and 0.82 respectively. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that participation in co-curricular activities and communication system were significantly related to teachers' job performance. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that Teachers should be involved in taking decisions on which co-curricular activities will positively contribute to their student's academic success for enhanced teachers job performance.

Keywords: Decision-making, Job performance, Co-curricular activities, Communication system,

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Introduction

Education is essential to people's lives because it helps individuals succeed in various spheres of life and also enhances their personal satisfaction. Osinbajo (2019) explained that education is the finest investment that people can make in their lives because educated individuals are more likely to find satisfying employment. He further expressed that it is through education that students and adults are empowered to actively participate in the development of their society. The educational policy guiding the educational system of the country is to ensure that individuals of different socio-cultural backgrounds have the same opportunity to education and to maintain quality at all levels of education. Education is accepted generally as an essential means for the human capital development of a nation (prasad & Gupta, 2020). Therefore, education serves as a tool for human cognitive, affective and psychomotor development.

According to the national policy on education, one of secondary education's goals is to motivate students to have a strong drive for success and self-reformation in school and later in life. Students in secondary education range in age from 11 to 18. At this stage, student abilities are shown, talents are discovered, students are equipped with relevant knowledge for survival, and students are able to ponder and reverence the opinions of others (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014). The success of educational activities in secondary schools depends on the job performance of the teachers. Teachers are the most valuable resources in educational systems. The teachers' preparation for this noble job entails their personalities, hard work, painstaking, right frame of mind, kindness, cheerfulness, dignity and zeal, among others.

It seems education at this stage is facing some challenges. Recent happenings in secondary schools have shown that teachers have not been up and performing their duties in the school system. For instance, in the case of Downen College Secondary School in Lagos State, some of the students bullied another student without the knowledge of the teachers, which led to the death of the student (Taylor, 2021). The drug and rape case of Chrisland high school students in Lagos State, which happened in Dubai during the World School Games, and the teachers that accompanied the students to the event were blamed for a lack of effective monitoring and negligence (Daniel, 2022). Also, a student who was electrocuted during interhouse sports at Chrisland High School in Lagos State (Onanuga & Amadi, 2023) is an indication that teachers seem to be failing in discharging their duties. Also, the behaviour of secondary school students these days is quite worrisome; some students hardly respect their elders and lack relevant skills and knowledge, which can negatively impact teacher job performance.

Classroom management is an area of teachers job performance that entails the practice of making sure that instructional activities in the classroom continue without interruption from students. Classroom management is the systematic arrangement of students, the classroom setting, and instructional resources to meet the intended learning goals (Ajayi & Ajayi, 2017). Classroom management involves the seating arrangement of students, which shows students seated in rows in front of the teacher, who is positioned close to the blackboard and teacher's capacity to keep an eye on specific types of activity in the classroom

(Adzongo & Olaitan, 2019). However, it has been observed that some classrooms are overpopulated in secondary schools in Ekiti State (Babalola & Awe, 2021). There are few or no passages for teachers to move around in order to check the activities of students in the classroom. Overcrowded classrooms in secondary schools appear to be a big challenge to effective classroom management, which could affect teachers job performance. However, Onwe, as stated in Oparaji (2022), opined that increased enrollment without a corresponding increase in personnel and material resources could result in congestion in the classroom, which could affect both the supervision of classwork and the monitoring of students' activities. This could affect teachers job performance.

Teachers' preparation of lessons is another area of teachers job performance, which entails all the preparation a teacher would have done before teaching in the classroom. Preparation of lessons involves the choice of topics, the ability of the teacher to identify the learning objectives, choosing teaching methods if the topic involves practical work by dividing students into groups for group work, e.g., fine art, and designing assessments to measure if students have achieved the learning objectives (Osatimehin et al., 2022). In the preparation of a lesson, materials are needed to construct the content of the topic chosen, and with the use of these materials, teachers are able to outline the learning objectives. Observation shows that textbooks are made available to teachers for the preparation of lessons (Ekiti State Ministry of Education, 2014). However, it was also observed that some teachers are deficient in the preparation of their lessons in the sense that their lesson notes appear not to be up to date. Also, some teachers lesson notes appear not to be well prepared. This could affect the teachers in lesson delivery, which can negatively impact teachers' job performance.

Attendance registers, which are part of record keeping in secondary schools, are an area of teachers job performance. It is used to keep records of the presence and absence of each student on a daily basis by their class teachers. It shows the record of students who attend school regularly, and it is usually kept by the class teacher. Although the attendance register is supposed to be marked both in the morning and afternoon to ascertain whether the student is present in school at a particular time or not. However, it appears that some teachers seem to mark the attendance register only in the morning without any attempt to mark it in the afternoon, while some students answer the call of their names in the morning and later disappear from school. This is a clear manifestation of an unhealthy professional attitude, which may lead to poor job performance by teachers. If such a student gets involved in a criminal act outside the school or unfortunately dies, it may cause a serious problem for the teacher and the school at large (Abubakar & Ogunode, 2021). It appears some teachers seem to allow the class captain to mark the attendance register, who might mark his friend present in school while the student is absent from school. This may contribute to the poor job performance of teachers while discharging their duties.

Teaching in the classroom is also an area of teachers job performance, which involves imparting knowledge according to what is approved in the lesson plan. This implies teachers have to be well versed in the subject matter in achieving the lesson specified objectives. While teaching, the teacher is expected to teach and write the salient points, from known to

unknown, and to effectively make use of the chalkboard (Limon & Nartgun, 2020). Moreover, for there to be effective teaching in the classroom, there is a need for effective communication, an adequate lesson plan, the organization of the classroom, and the engagement of students in the lesson. It appears that some teachers do not have good mastery of the subject matter, and this could hinder the academic performance of students, which may erode the quality job performance of teachers in imparting knowledge to students (Okpara & Nwabia, 2022).

In secondary schools, giving and marking students' assignments is a common practice, and it is another area of teachers job performance. Assignments are mainly meant to reinforce learning through the practice of what is taught in the classroom, which enhances students' understanding on the topic taught. Assignments give students the freedom to choose how to show what they have learned in the classroom (Ekwueme et al., 2018). They do this, abiding by the teacher's instructions either through writing, speaking, drawing, or building. Giving students assignments enables them to learn better, especially when what is being taught is grounded in real-world situations, which gives them the opportunity to apply what they have learned in an engaging and relevant environment (Oluwafemi et al., 2019). However, it appears some teachers seem not to give assignments, and some appear to be lazy to mark assignments due to an overwhelming workload and a lack of motivation. Failure to mark assignments is an indication of a lack of responsibility, which makes it difficult to determine if students have met the specified learning goals (Obilor, 2020). This could result in poor job performance by teachers.

The observed poor job performance of teachers could be linked to participation in decision-making in the areas of co-curricular activities and communication system.

Literature Review

Co-curriculars are activities pursued at a school in addition to the normal course of study (Othoo & Omondi, 2022). Co-curricular activities are areas where teachers are to participate in making decisions in the school system because the teachers are closer to the students and understand how each student assimilates what is taught in the classroom (Bekomson et al., 2020). The school co-curricular activities refer to all the activities that balance and enhance what students learn from the school. Some of the co-curricular activities are school choir, painting, drama, music, debate, barbers club, reading club, social groups, school athletics team, excursion, leadership roles such as school prefects, tie and dye, baking, dancing group, fashion designing, news club, French club, and beadmaking, among others (Oke & Ichima 2020). Although it is believed that co-curricular activities add value to students, they also help to build their talents and expose them to leadership roles (Ogunseemi et al., 2021). Teachers sometimes engage their students in co-curricular activities in order to enhance what is taught in the classroom (Itankan, 2020). A French teacher can encourage his students to join the French club in order to help the students understand French better through the interactions, debate, drama and excursions they experience in the French club and as a result, teachers' job performance will be enhanced (Ogwunte et al., 2022). When teachers are partake in decision-making as regards co-curricular activities in the school, teachers themselves will participate in the co-curricular activities and ensure that the school

organizes frequent co-curricular activities (Utsa et al., 2021). Teachers will also suggest better co-curricular activities that would benefit and enhance learning and encourage students to join any subject-related co-curricular activities that could enhance student academic success (Omage, 2018). When students are able to perform well in their academics, teachers job performance will be elevated.

Moreover, communication is the mode through which instructions are passed on to the students in the schools. The function of communication cannot be underestimated within the school because teachers and students acquire information through communication. Teachers are involved in communication when teaching, discipling, conducting examinations, conducting oral interview and organizing co-curricular activities to transfer information from the sender, which is the teacher, to the receiver, which is the student (Wordu et al., 2022). The communication system refers to various methods, channels and tools through which information is transmitted and exchanged among teachers, students and administrators in the school (Yawe & Bua, 2016). An effective flow of information, either written, verbal or digital, from the principal to the teachers, among teachers and students, could enable the school to achieve its aims and objectives and enhance better administration in the school system (Abiodun-Oyebanji, 2019).

The communication system is an area where teachers are to participate in making decisions in the school because teachers equip students with relevant knowledge and also produce secondary school output. Communication tools are very important for effective teaching and learning in the school system (Nwosu, 2017). This was evident during the pandemic when teachers working in private secondary schools were able to continue their classes with the use of ICT, while teachers working in public secondary schools were unable to continue their classes until the government reopened the schools for physical activities (Ettang, 2020; Owoyemi & Moju, 2021). Involving teachers in decision-making with regard to the communication system will enable them to make their opinion known about the need for various communication tools that can enhance their job performance in the school (Chinasa, 2022). Also, a Chemistry teacher can enhance his teaching on 'reaction of chemicals', with the use of a video of how chemicals react; likewise, a Biology teacher can use an enlarged 3D image to enhance his lesson on the topic 'types of bone', and students can be assessed through online assessment tools that can track the progress of each student and identify areas where they need additional support (Ngwakwe et al., 2018). Moreover, teachers would be able to explore different channels to disseminate information among themselves and to their students, which would improve their job performance (Oladimeji et al., 2018).

Teachers' job performance refers to tasks carried out by teachers, such as teaching, assessment, marking student tests and examination scripts, and record-keeping at a specific time in the classroom to achieve educational goals (Olorunsola & Oyeleye, 2019). This implies that it is impossible for a teacher who lacks knowledge of subject matter or is lazy to mark the attendance register to perform their job in that area effectively. Oparaji et al. (2021), attested that it is regarded as unethical for a teacher to lose interest in his behavioral duties in the school in terms of lesson preparation, teaching, record keeping, and punctuality to school, as it could affect the teachers' job performance and hinder the goal achievement of the school.

According to Emengin et al. (2020), teachers' job performance can be described as a two-way performance, which is in-role and extra-role. He explains further that in-role performance is about the actions of the teacher that fulfill the standard in accordance with the job description, while extra-role performance refers to the teacher's actions that are outside the official requirements of his job. This implies that teachers perform their duties in line with their job description, such as lesson preparation, teaching, record keeping, classroom management, assessment of students and also take part in activities in the school such as decision making, the disciplinary committee, the housemaster, and the examination committee, which leads to the achievement of school goals (Odu-dikoro, 2022). According to Chukwueze (2023) teachers job performance is considered to be very important if the school system is to be effective, because teachers who are passionate about their job are highly productive and they exhibit behaviours like preparing their lesson notes on time, showing up early for class, guiding the students, teaching their students on time, helping the students with their assignments, marking attendance registers as when due, and encouraging students to participate in co-curricular activities (Haryaka & Sjamsir, 2021). Abiodun-Oyebanji (2021), described teachers who perform well in their job as teachers who are knowledgeable in their subjects, who effectively develop their lesson plans, who are able to carry out their teaching duties, and who succeed in other duties entrusted to them. Olorunsola and Aina (2022) reiterated that job performance is a major requirement of any organization because, to a large extent, it has a great effect on the success of the organization. They further said it is an indicator in determining the success or failure of the organization. Hence, there is a need for organizations to repeatedly improve the performance of their staff.

Purpose of the Study

It seeks to establish the relationship between participation in co-curricular activities and teachers job performance. It is to establish the relationship between participation in communication system and teachers job performance in secondary schools in Ekiti State

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses are formulated for the purpose of this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between participation in co-curricular activities and teachers job performance.
2. There is no significant relationship between participation in communication system and teachers job performance.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. The population of the study consisted of 7,177 teachers and 202 principals in all the 202 public secondary schools in the sixteen local government areas in Ekiti State (Source: Ministry of Education, 2025). The sample for the study consisted of 384 respondents which made up of 24 principals and 360 teachers. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure.

In the first stage, simple random sampling techniques was used to select two senatorial districts from the three senatorial districts in the state. In the second stage, three Local

Governments were randomly selected from each of the senatorial district. In stage three, 24 public secondary schools were purposively selected from the six Local Government areas. In the final stage, simple random sampling technique was used to select 15 teachers from each of the school.

Two sets of instruments tagged Participation in Co-curricular activities and Communication system Questionnaire (PCCQ) and Teachers Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ) were used to collect data. The face and content validity were done by experts to determine the appropriateness of the instruments and making sure the contents were well represented. The reliability of the instruments was established using test-retest method. The instruments were administered to the respondents twice within an interval of two weeks. The collected data were analyzed using Pearson Moment Correlation Analysis. A reliability coefficient of 0.86 and 0.82 were obtained respectively. The coefficients were considered high enough to conclude that the instruments are reliable. The descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data collected. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between participation in co-curricular activities and teachers job performance.

In testing this hypothesis, data on teachers job performance were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of TPJQ item (1- 30) in the questionnaire. Data on participation in co-curricular activities were collected from the responses of the respondents to the items under Section B of PCCQ item (1 - 5) in the questionnaire. Both were subjected to statistical analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Relationship between Participation in Co-Curricular Activities and Teachers Job Performance

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r-cal	P-value
Participation in co-curricular activities	24	15.12	0.92	0.627*	0.001
Teachers job performance	24	101.83	11.74		

* $p < 0.05$ (Significant Result)

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Table 1 showed that the r-cal value (0.627) is significant at $p < 0.05$ level of significance, because p-value 0.001 is < 0.05 . The null hypothesis was therefore rejected. This implies that there was a significant relationship between participation in co-curricular activities and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The correlation between participation in co-curricular activities and teachers job performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State is moderate and statistically significant in a positive direction.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between participation in communication system and teachers job performance.

In testing this hypothesis, data on teachers job performance were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of TPJQ item (1- 30) in the questionnaire. Data on participation in communication system were collected from the responses of the respondents to the items under Section B of PCCQ item (6 – 10) in the questionnaire. Both were subjected to statistical analysis using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 2

Table 2: Relationship between Participation in Communication System and Teachers

Variable	Job Performance			r-cal	P-value
	N	Mean	SD		
Participation in communication system	24	14.52	0.73	0.423*	0.039
Teachers job performance	24	101.83	11.74		

* $p < 0.05$ (Significant Result)

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Table 2 showed that the r-cal value (0.423) is significant at $p < 0.05$ level of significance, because p-value 0.039 is < 0.05 . The null hypothesis was therefore rejected. This implies that there was a significant relationship between participation in communication system and teachers job performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The correlation between participation in communication system and teachers job performance in public secondary schools in Ekiti State is moderate and statistically significant in a positive direction.

Discussion

The study showed that there was significant relationship between participation in co-curricular activities and teachers job performance. It equally means that for teachers job performances to be enhanced, effective participation in co-curricular activities is inevitable and indispensable in the school system. This finding resulted from the fact that the government and school principal have realized that When teachers are involved in making decision as regard co-curricular activities in the school, teachers themselves will participate in the co-curricular activities, ensure that the school organize frequent co-curricular activities, teachers will suggest better co-curricular activities that would benefit and enhance learning and encourage students to join any subject related co-curricular activities that could enhance student academic success. When students are able to perform well in their academic, teachers job performance will be elevated. The finding supports the research work of Muema, Kasivu and Mwanza (2019) who found that participation of secondary school teachers in co-curricular activities will give them the opportunity to ease their workload, bring to light their forgotten talents, enable the teachers to be able to train the students in co-curricular activities and enhance their job performance in the school system.

It was also found out that there was significant relationship between participation in communication system and teachers job performance. This by implication means that

participation in communication system influences teachers' job performance. This could be due to the fact that when teachers are involved in decision-making as regard communication system, teachers would be able to make their opinion known about the need for various communication tools that can enhance their job performance in the school. Also, when teachers are continually reminded of what they are to accomplish, confusion does not set in and they are able to work at their best. This finding is consistent with the submission of Amalu and Oyo-Ita (2023) that found a substantial correlation between information communication technology, in services training and teachers job performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, teachers participation in co-curricular activities and communication system in Ekiti State were quite encouraging. Consequently, this has enhanced the school goals and teachers job performance. Teachers participation in making decision as regard co-curricular activities had a positive effect on student academic achievement which had a direct effect on teacher job performance. Teachers participation in communication system especially in the use of information communication technology had also enhanced students academic performance which had a positive effect on teachers job performance. Participation in co-curricular activities and communication system were important factors that influenced teachers job performance in secondary school in Ekiti State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made

1. Teachers should be involved in taking decision on which co-curricular activities will positively contribute to their student's academic success for enhanced teachers job performance.
2. Teachers should encourage students to join subject-related co-curricular activities so as to improve their understanding on the subject for an enhanced teachers job performance.
3. There should be an open line of communication system with an effective feedback mechanism for enhanced teachers job performance

Teachers should encourage students to study further with the use of ICT for better assimilation which will have a positive effect on teachers job

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